

The contribution of groundwater to total ET was maximum when plants were irrigated at 25% available soil moisture depletion at 0-30 cm depth. In drier regimes, the rice plant failed to extract moisture from the groundwater table, although the gradient of water potential was maximum. Liquid phase continuity was disturbed under the drier soil regimes, reducing groundwater contribution to a minimum. ■

Response of rice varieties to nitrogen manuring at Tirur, India

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A field trial during *sornavari* 1980 (May-June to August-September) stu-

Grain yields (t/ha) of 6 rices treated with 5 nitrogen levels at Tirur, India.

Varieties	Grain yield (t/ha)					Mean	Fertilizer index
	No N	40kg N/ha	80 kg N/ha	120kg N/ha	160 kg N/ha		
AS1374	3.1	3.9	4.4	5.5 ^a	4.9	4.3	1.3
TM3207	2.8	3.4	4.0	4.3	4.7 ^a	3.8	1.2
TM2871	2.9	3.8	3.8	4.4	5.0 ^a	4.0	1.3
TM2048	2.8	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.3 ^a	3.1	1.2
TM1898	3.2	3.8	4.8	5.0	5.6 ^a	4.5	1.3
TKM9	3.6	4.0	5.0	5.6 ^a	5.5	4.7	1.2
Mean	3.1	3.7	4.3	4.8	5.0		
				F-test	SE	CD	
Variety				S**	0.095	0.541	
N levels				S**	0.053	0.345	
Interactions:							
				N level × variety	S**	0.088	0.347
				Variety × N level	S**	0.103	0.561

^a Highest optimum yields. **Significant at 0.99 level.

died the yield potential of pre-release cultures under different levels of nitrogen fertilizer (N). Six rice varieties and five N levels were tested in a split-plot design replicated twice (see table).

Yield differences were statistically significant for the interaction of nitrogen levels and rice varieties. TKM9 had the highest yield at all N levels of treatment, but had low response to N. ■

Contribution of seedling quality to rice production

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The contribution of seedling quality to grain yield and growth duration of transplanted rice was studied in the cold, dry, and wet seasons. High quality seedlings were produced by giving better management in the nursery; poor qual-

ity ones were obtained from a poorly managed nursery. A physical seedling quality index (SQI) was calculated (Table 1) and used for correlation analysis with yield, growth duration, and seedling strength measured in milligrams of dry matter produced per centimeter length of seedling.

The SQI correlated strongly with seedling strength (Table 2). SQ had no influence on grain yield and was negatively associated with growth duration. But high quality seedlings shortened crop growth duration by at least 6-10 days. ■

Table 1. Sample calculation of the physical quality index for rice seedlings, BRRI.

Seedling ht (cm)	Seedling ^a color rate (A)	Seedling strength (mg dry matter/cm) (B)	Seedling quality	
			(A) (B)	Index
11.1	5	8.97	44.9	100
11.1	5	7.57	37.8	84
10.1	4	5.51	22.0	49
10.3	4	4.11	16.4	36
9.2	2	6.33	12.7	28
8.9	2	4.20	8.4	18
9.0	1	3.50	3.5	8
9.8	1	2.65	2.55	6

^a 5-1 : deep green - yellow.

Table 2. Relationships among seedling quality and grain yield, growth duration, and seedling strength. BRRI.

Season	Variety	Correlation coefficient ^a		
		Yield	Growth duration (days)	Seedling strength
Boro, 1980	BR3	-.522	-.727*	.927**
	BR7	-.006	-.233	.965**
Boro, 1981	BR3	.678	-.838**	.901**
	BR9	.376	-.834**	.963**
Aus, 1981	BR3	.439	-.305	.894**
Aman, 1981	BR4	.529	-.845**	.990**

^a *significant at .05 level; **significant at .01 level.

Effect of planting time and density on yields of short-duration rice varieties

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Field experiments during the kharif (wet) season 1975-77 at the Crop Research Centre (29° N lat, 79.3 E long, 243.84 m altitude) explored the effect of